
Assessing AI Literacy and Readiness in the Thailand's Workforce: Challenges and Opportunities for Digital Transformation

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ABSTRACT

As the rapid advancement of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has recently been proved as a critical component of our digital transformation which impacts multiple dimensions of human's life like economic, social, and cultural aspects etc. Since AI technologies keep evolving, it provides opportunities for human to enhance productivity efficiency, and innovation across multiple sectors while it also denotes the challenges that required to discuss to employ their benefits and mitigate potential risks in the future. The comprehends of these opportunities and challenges is crucial to leveraging AI. It is imperative to understand both in how AI could be further implemented to Thailand's workforce to improve capabilities and readiness. Hence, this research aims to assess the present state of AI literacy and readiness in Thailand's workforce and fine recommendations in proposals for policymakers to enhance AI skills development initiatives by focusing on the workforce's awareness to integrate AI into their operational job. This study could highlight the importance of equipping individuals' necessary skills until to thrive to be AI-driven economy country. The research employs a modified Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) framework in evaluation of factors influencing AI adoption, proficiency and the workforce's intention to use AI systems. In order to gather relevant data, the researcher has conducted online questionnaire surveys, targeting Thailand's workforce across industries, with the target of 318 respondents from various demographical workforce. This questionnaire aims to focus on important variables such as the perceived usefulness of AI, perceived ease of use AI, social influence, facilitating conditions, AI literacy and behavioral intention to use AI. In addition, this research also aims to examine the potential fears that could hinder AI skills development. It is essential to identify these barriers for developing strategies to encourage AI adoption and could be benefit for policymakers to create environment to embrace AI technology advancement. The findings from this research aims to directly support both the private and public sector to adopt AI skills effectively and bridging

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the gap between digital literacy skills and the necessary skills to enhance the workforce's readiness for the future of AI-driven economic development, not only enhancing technical skills should be involved but fostering mindset open to continuous learning and adaptation as part of policies. Fostering an open mindset is proved to be necessitating to a more AI- integrated workforce. Not only is it beneficial to this cause of integrating AI into the workforce but also for overall workforce readiness to the new workforce landscape where many technologies and skillsets are being integrated into workplace. Therefore, a comprehensive strategy that includes updating educational curricula, promoting intersectoral collaborations, and investing in lifelong learning platforms will proves to be beneficial to the long-term advancement of the workforce in general. This research aims to find solutions that ensures all segments of the population are equipped with the tools needed for upcoming changes and disruption, thus preventing a divide between different socio-economic groups. Ultimately, this research aims to support Thailand's transition towards AI-driven economy by ensuring that its workforce is well-prepared for upcoming development and changes. By equipping workforce with the AI-related necessary skills and knowledge, Thailand can harness the full potential of AI technologies to drive innovation and economic growth while mitigating potential risks associated with technological disruption. With strategic planning and implementation of effective policies, Thailand can position itself as a leader by shift into the next level and embracing digital transformation in region.

Keywords: About five keywords or phrases in alphabetical order, separated by semicolons.

AI literacy; workforce readiness; digital transformation; technology adoption

1. Introduction

As Artificial Intelligence (AI) is increasingly transforming the workforce worldwide, reinforcing digitalization and reshaping how businesses operate. As many opportunities AI's rapid changes may bring, so do challenges, in particular for developing countries like Thailand where AI has extreme potential to enhance and maintain global competitiveness. In integration of AI technologies into Thailand's industries, the potential to enhance productivity, streamline operations and foster innovation is high. However, to what extent that potential can be achieved will highly depend on the readiness and literacy of the workforce. Without these necessary digital literacy skills, the potential benefits of AI-driven workforce could be hindered and further aggravate the divide between workforce and digitalization [1].

Presently, the Thai workforce is at a critical intersection, in need of both policy-driven and comprehensive education and training programs to promote AI literacy and readiness, Thailand's economic growth will have to rely on the proper alignment of its workforce's skills in correspondence with the increasing demand for AI proficiency in the modern world. There have been researches that indicates the AI literacy influences acceptance and proficiency in using AI systems, making it vital to understand how prepared the Thai workforce is in adoption of AI technologies. [1].

As a key component in its broader vision for digital transformation, Thailand has outlined a national AI strategy and action plan for 2022-2027. The plan involves of five key strategies which is designed to establish a robust AI ecosystem that further enhances both the economy and the quality of life of Thai citizens. Among those five key strategies are 15 work plans, expanding the focus from ethics, infrastructure human capacity, innovation, and AI applications. Some of the specific targets included raising AI awareness among its 600,000 citizens, enforcing AI-related legislatures and

regulations, and cultivating over 30,000 AI talents within the span of six years. The plan further prioritized AI adoption in 10 key industries including from government services, agriculture, healthcare, finance, and manufacturing to drive innovation and efficiency. As a result of this plan's announcement, Thailand has improved its global standing in AI readiness from 59th to 31st in the Government AI Readiness Index between 2021 and 2022. Many key initiatives like the development of a national AI service platform, the establishment of supercomputer infrastructure, and the Super AI Engineer workforce development programmers which are pivotal to achieving these goals. A strong emphasis is then placed on ethical AI development, with efforts to create comprehensive AI ethics guidelines and governance frameworks to guide responsible AI use [2][3].

Therefore, this study employs a modified Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) framework. The UTAUT framework provides an extensive structure that can be used to analyze factors such as performance expectancy (PE), effort expectancy (EE), social influence (SI), and facilitating conditions (FC) which could influence AI adoption. Furthermore, AI-related anxiety will also be introduced as one a key variable, recognizing that anxiety caused by gaps of AI literacy can be arbitrated.

This research's methodology consists of an online survey questionnaire that was distributed across various workforce in Thailand's industries. Using statistical techniques such as descriptive statistics, multiple regression analysis and Structural Equation Modelling (SEM), the researcher was able to investigate the relationship between independent variable (PU, PE, SI, FC) and dependent variables such as AI acceptance, performance expectancy and intention to use which reflects as workforce readiness. This approach provides a comprehensive understanding of many

factors influencing AI adoption and digital skill development in Thailand, offering key insights and compass the direction for policymakers, furthermore businesses sector can foster a digitally empowered workforce.

2. Literature Review

2.1 AI Literacy / AI Skill

AI literacy or AI skill typically refers to an individuals' ability to comprehend, utilize, and critically evaluating AI technologies, a skill that is increasingly demanded in modern digital economies [4]. The importance of AI literacy spans over many sectors as it tends to prepare individuals with essential skills to leverage and enhance productivity as well as efficiency through the use AI tools [4]. In present day's workforce, the capability to interact and utilize with AI systems effectively does not only benefits individual's performance and capabilities but businesses' ability to maintain its competency through optimized operations, driven by AI tools. While AI tools are accepted across various industries, there has been a growing concern that workers across the workforce must acquire certain AI-related competencies and skills. Some workforce demographics, late-career-stage workers, for example, can be proved beneficial from AI literacy training. Through those training, these workers can bring about a mix of extensive industry experience in combination with AI skills, can create valuable contributions to the digital economy [5]. There can even be new career path, emerge from the rise of AI. For instance, prompt engineering, is a role where individuals with extensive domain knowledge refines AI outputs based on their extensive experience [5]. This trend suggests that AI literacy is not only about technical proficiency but also the capability in applying AI within the specific given context to generate favorable outputs.

In an effort to bridge the skills gap in today's workforce, developing educational

strategies that can promote AI literacy should be highlighted as one of the most prominent as it provides tangible benefits of AI tools, as studies have shown that performance expectancy significantly influences the intention to adopt these technologies [4]. This has been proven correct, specifically for younger learners and students, who not only required to understand how AI tools function but also to utilize it for their practical applications and limitations in their own academic and professional contexts in the future.

Therefore, an integrative and multidisciplinary approach to AI is proved to be crucial. As Margaryan (2023) elaborates that the need for an approach that brings together insights from social sciences, engineering and computer science to create comprehensive AI literacy programs is essential for a more digitalized economy. These programs should not only cover technical skills but also on critical thinking skills, which altogether creates a so-called "fusion skill" which combines ethical AI use with comprehensive understanding of AI. This will allow the workforce to collaborate with AI effectively and proficiently [5]. This approach further advocates for a more holistic reform of the business education to further integrate AI literacy into their programs in ensuring that future business and workforce personnels are well-equipped to work alongside AI systems. [5].

This transformation in work environment practices due to the advancement of AI required a continuous adaptation of skills and knowledge. Chetty (2023) and Babashahi et al. (2024) argues that AI literacy can and should be a part of lifelong learning, providing that many professionals today will have to experience rapid technological advancement for years to come. Moreover, metacognitive skills, the set of skills that allows an individual with the ability to reflect on one's cognitive process while using AI systems, are proved critical. While AI continues to advance and evolves,

the workforce, too, shall adapt to understand the capabilities and the limitations of AI in order to utilize them effectively in decision making and problem solve processes [6]. AI literacy, therefore, proved vital for workers at every stage in their careers. It is not a set of skills that is preferable but required to enhances individual performance and ensure that the economy can continues to leverage AI technologies for innovation and long-term growth

2.2 Anxiety with AI Technology

The unanticipated adoption of AI across multiple industries has introduced to the workforce both optimistic and pessimistic impressions. AI anxiety, defined as the fear or an uneasy feeling associated with the use of AI technologies, can significantly influence job performance and the individual's ability to comprehend and adopt AI into their daily professional lives. The root causes of the anxiety stems from concerns of one's job security, the potential of AI to be misused, or the ability of adapt to the rapid changes of technological environments [7]. These anxieties tend to be prevalent particularly among the older workers or those with lower technical self-efficacy, creating barriers to AI adoption in the workplace [8].

AI anxiety can have a direct, negative impact on work performance. Research have shown that anxiety related to AI tools, in particular for high-stakes environment like in healthcare or government, can hinder the effective use of AI-enabled systems. For example, in clinical settings, there can be anxiety associated with AI-based decision-making systems which, in turn, reduced the job performance. The cause for AI anxiety in this example can be traced to how many healthcare practitioners hesitates to rely on AI tools for critical decisions [8]. Furthermore, many studies have also highlighted that the job autonomy and psychological well-being of the employees can positively influence the effects of AI anxiety by providing employees by

mitigating the fears of job replacement and provide them with greater sense of control [9]. By ensuring that employees would have full autonomy over their work process, the overall AI anxiety in workplace can be significantly reduced [9].

AI anxiety can have negative correlations with AI acceptance. A meta-analysis of healthcare practitioners' use of AI-enabled clinical decision support systems of AI-CDSSs founded that anxiety is one of the significant predictors of lower acceptance and intentions to use AI systems [8]. Many practitioners who have high levels of experiences with AI are less likely to trust and adopt these systems in the future, even when provided with proper literacy trainings and potential benefits AI could bring. This suggests that in addressing AI anxiety, training and educational interventions could further enhance the overall acceptance of AI technologies in the workplace but might not be able to address every AI anxiety given the uniqueness of each situation and circumstances.

Some research suggests that AI anxiety plays a mediating role between the relationship of AI literacy and AI acceptance. While those with high AI literacy are more likely to trust and accept the AI systems into their professional career, some with lower AI literacy are more repellent of AI systems with AI anxiety being the core barrier to further AI learning and usage, diminishing its positive effect of literacy on AI acceptance [8]. This further underscore the importance of not only improving the AI literacy but also to actively addressing the sources of anxiety in an effort to foster a more AI-proficient workforce.

One of the particularly striking forms of AI anxiety is existential anxiety, which defines the fears of AI's impact on the future of humanity as a whole. One of the studies conducted in Saudi Arabia shows that over 96% of respondents expressed existential fears related to AI, including concerns about death, the unpredictability of fate, and ethical

dilemmas of AI usage [7]. Such anxieties are particularly pronounced among older age groups and individuals in precarious employment situations, especially employees that are divorced or widowed [7].

Another concept that is closely related to AI anxiety is the concept of technostress, which defines the stress individuals' experiences while adopting newer technologies. Technostress can be categorized into two categories: challenge and hindrance stressors. Challenge stressors are perceived as opportunities for growth while hindrance stressors evoke negative connotations such as anxiety. Research has indicated that while some workers may view AI as a challenge that further promotes skill development, others experience heightened anxiety due to technical difficulties and fear of obsolescence which further hinder AI adoption [6]. Therefore, technical self-efficacy plays a moderating role in this relationship where workers with higher self-efficacy are less likely to experience AI anxiety and are likely to adopt AI as a growth opportunity [6].

2.3 AI Acceptance / AI Adoption

The acceptance of AI is a crucial factor in its successful implementation within various industries. The Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) provides a fundamental framework for the understanding of AI acceptance. The framework highlights key factors such as performance expectancy (PE), effort expectancy (EE), social influence (SI), and facilitating conditions (FC) as primary predictors of the behavioral intentions to use AI technologies [11]. UTAUT has been widely applied to study AI adoption across sectors, revealing that these factors significantly influence employees' and organizations' willingness to embrace AI [10]. Performance expectancy or the perceived usefulness of AI, then often emerges as the strongest predictor of acceptance, particularly in industries that

heavily relies on AI for operational efficiency.

AI literacy is also another crucial factor in AI acceptance. The higher levels of AI literacy, the higher the intention to adopt AI tools. As noted by Li and Kim (2024), AI literacy does not only enhance workers' competency but also reduces AI anxiety and consequently leads to higher acceptance rates. In the European exhibition industry, for instance, a lack of AI literacy has been noted as one of the significant barriers to AI adoption, especially in smaller organizations wherein financial and technological resources are limited [12].

Trust also plays a pivotal role of AI acceptance. Researchers found that trust significantly influences behavioral intentions to utilize AI, especially in industries where AI is used to handle sensitive tasks [10]. This trust factor is particularly relevant to many AI-driven systems like chatbots and AI-enabled decision support systems, where each user must solely rely on the technology to deliver both accurate and reliable outcomes. Trust, therefore, is not only build on the performance of AI but also on its transparency and alignment with user expectations [10].

The readiness in adoption of AI highly varies across different industries as it is influenced by several organizational factors. Hradecky et al. (2022) found that organizational size, financial resources, and the strength of internal technological practices, such as IT infrastructure, in the European exhibition sector are key technological resources which are more likely to adopt AI since they can mitigate the associated risks and costs. Moreover, data management and protection concerns, especially after COVID-19 pandemic, have further heightened the need for safer, more secure AI systems that can comply with data privacy regulations. This strategic approach, combined with tangible management support and employee training programs, are proved essential in fostering a positive environment for AI adoption [12].

The future success of AI adoption also highly depends on whether organizations are technologically ready and there is sufficient training provided to its employees. All employees need to be equipped with the sufficient skill set to use AI effectively and proper training programs can address the insecurities and anxieties involved the use of AI and its adoption [12]. As Li and Kim

(2024) emphasized, developing AI literacy within organizations is essential for human resource development (HRD) and that it should be prioritized. Competencies with AI and technology should include the understanding of its relevance, values, and ethical implications in order to navigate through the evolving technological landscape.